

The Impact of Junk Food Consumption on Mental Health among Healthcare Workers: A Narrative Review

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Abstract

Background: This narrative review explored the prevalence of junk food (JF) consumption and its detrimental effects on the health and mental well-being of healthcare workers (HCWs) as well as to assess the obstacles preventing the adoption of healthy eating habits in its workplace.

Methods: By searching websites for studies to be enrolled in this review in the period from 2014 to 2024, 81 studies were found on the PubMed website and 33 on other websites, for a total of 114 studies. 68 studies were prepared that did not fit our topic, leaving 46 studies that were classified as follows: 14 studies for HCWs, 8 nursing studies, 18 medical student studies and 6 studies in others.

Results: This review emphasizes the prevalence of JFs consumption habits among different HCWs, trends of JFs consumption among both gender of HCWs, barriers to healthy eating habits at the workplace, possible associations among participant's demographics, job nature and JF consumption at work as well as the prevalence of overweight and obesity among HCWs and lastly, impact of JFs on mental health and work outcomes among HCWs were discussed.

Conclusion: The evidence from this narrative review has provided enough information about effects of JF consumption on the health and mental well-being of HCWs. Future studies can assess how new strategies to encourage healthier eating among HCWs affect diet quality and more general measures of health and wellbeing.

Introduction

Problem Description

Recently, it has been observed that the prevalence of overweight and obesity has increased throughout the world [48], and one of the reasons that has led to this is the trend towards junk food (JF) consumption. Often due to heavy workloads, stressful work environments, irregular work schedules, unhealthy eating habits due to workload, insufficient rest time, and unavailability of healthy food in the hospital, many healthcare workers (HCWs) often sacrifice their physical and emotional needs in an attempt to provide appropriate medical care to patients.

Available Knowledge

A healthy lifestyle is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as a combination of four principles: regular physical activity, a tobacco-free

lifestyle, good eating habits, and a setting that promotes social and emotional well-being. Of them, a nutritious diet is the most crucial [1].

Junk foods (JF) refers to food that is high in fat, sugar and salt content but in low nutritional values. JF's flavor, availability, ready-to-eat packaging, and ease of preparation have all contributed to its steadily rising consumption. Even while people are well aware of JF's negative effects, they nevertheless prefer it [2].

Eating JF may impair immunological function, damage physical and mental development, and increase susceptibility to a number of particular and general illnesses in general population as well as HCWs [3]. JF can also affect the physical and emotional well-being of HCWs [4] and, ultimately, the quality of care they provide [5]. Conversely, consuming a nutritious diet was linked to mental health. Consuming more fruits

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Keywords:

Junk food,
healthcare workers,
mental health.

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and vegetables, for example, has been linked to a decreased chance of developing depression [6].

Therefore, there is a strong enough correlation between JF and mental health issues. There should be a consistent public education and awareness effort to avoid mental disease by making dietary and lifestyle changes, primarily to shield HCWs from chronic mental health issues.

Specific Aims

Through the collection of data from recent meta-analyses and observational studies, which are a trustworthy source of evidence over the last 10 years, sought to assess the relationship between mental health difficulties and JFs intake consumption among HCWs.

Objectives:

Primary objectives

- To determine the prevalence of JFs consumption habits among different HCWs.
- To compare the trends of JFs consumption among both gender of HCWs (males and females).
- To assess barriers to healthy eating habits at the workplace.
- To explore possible associations among participant's demographics, job nature and JF consumption at work.

Secondary objectives

- Determine the prevalence of overweight and obesity among HCWs.
- Determine the impact of JFs on mental health and work outcomes among HCWs.

Subjects and Methods

Study Design

Narrative review study

Study Methods

The PubMed, Web of Science, Science Direct, Google Scholar, and SCOPUS database were searched for cross-sectional, recent meta-analysis and observational studies published between 2014 and 2024, with the following words; junk food, fast food, takeaway food, takeout food, food behavior, healthcare workers, medical students, doctors, nurses, obesity, mental health, depression, psychiatric disorders.

Ethical approval has been documented from Scientific Research Center, Prince Sultan Military Medical City, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia under IRB approval No: E-2300, at 21st March, 2024.

Inclusion Criteria

- Meta-analysis or observational studies included JFs among any subclass of HCWs that assessed by validated scales.
- Mental health, depression, psychiatric disorders were the primary or secondary outcome and assessed by validated scales.

- Meta-analysis or observational studies presented comprehensive data on the relation between JF and psychological disorders.

- Presence or absence of clinically diagnosed depression in the studied population was described.

Exclusion Criteria

- Meta-analysis or observational studies included JFs among any subclass of HCWs that assessed by non-validated scales.

- Mental health, depression, psychiatric disorders were not the outcome or their assessment was questionable in terms of our review.

- The comprehensive data on the relation between JF and psychological disorders was not provided in meta-analysis or subgroups.

- Presence or absence of clinically diagnosed depression in the studied population was not mentioned.

Healthcare Workers Include

- Doctors (juniors and consultants)
- Nurses
- Pharmacist
- Dentists
- Students
- Health workers.

Junk Foods Include

- Sweets (biscuits, cookies, cakes, chocolates, candies),
- Sweetened beverages (soda, soft drinks),
- Fast meals (hot dogs, hamburgers, cheeseburgers, fried chicken, pizza),
- Energy drinks and
- Salty snacks (chips, cheese curls, popcorn, pretzels) [49].

Data Collection

Articles were limited to human participants only and papers in the English language only were included. Despite slight variations between some of the definitions of junk food, fast food and takeaway food, the nutritional composition of these types of food is predominately unfavourable; therefore, literature on these definitions was included. The terminology used in this review fluctuates to represent the original studies. Therefore, the terminology used by the authors is dependent on the literature in review; in instances where 'takeaway' 'junk food' and 'fast foods' are discussed, the term 'junk foods' has been used [50]. The enrolled studies were categorized by multiple manners:

- Sources (authors, years).
- Source types.
- Participants HCW subclasses (medical students, doctors, nurses, dentists).
- Aim.
- Methods.
- Main findings.

Results

When researching websites for studies to be enrolled in this review in the period from 2014 to 2024, 81 studies were found on the PubMed website and 33 on other websites, for a total of 114 studies. 68 studies were

prepared that did not fit our topic, leaving 46 studies that were classified as follows: 14 studies for HCWs, 8 nursing studies, 18 medical student studies and 6 studies in others (flow chart).

Figure 1: Flow Chart of Enrolled Studies

Table 1: The Key Findings of Enrolled Studies during the Last 10 Years

Sources	Source types and country	Aim of the study	Participants	Methods	Main findings
Ahmad et al. 5015 [29]	cross-sectional, Pakistan	Effects of healthcare diet, exercise and mental wellbeing on lives e.g., sleep, BMI etc.	1,510 HCWs (doctors, dentists and nurses)	Warwick Edinburg Mental Wellbeing Scale (WEMWBS) was used to assess mental wellbeing, USDA Dietary Guidelines-2010 to quantify diet and American Heart Association (AHA) guidelines for the analysis of exercise.	76% did not perform any exercise. 71.5% worked >48 h/week. More than 50% of healthcare professionals were sleeping <7 h/day. WEMWBS score of the entire sample was 47.9
Almajwal, 2016 [14]	cross-sectional, Saudi Arabia	Association between stress, shift work, and	395 nurses	Dutch Eating Behavior Questionnaire	Stress, and shift duty influenced the amount of food

		eating behavior among non-Saudi female nurses working in Central Saudi Arab		(DEBQ) was used. The questionnaire contained items of socio-demographic data, body mass index, shift work, and hours worked per week.	nurses consumed. Higher % of nurses eating more fast food, snacks, and bingeing. High stressed nurses had higher DEBQ scores.
Han et al., 2016 [7]	cross-sectional, Korea	Dietary and health behaviors of Korean hospital nurses according to their work schedule type	340 nurses	Nurses' dietary and health behaviors were evaluated across different work schedules and compared to the general Korean female population.	Nurses with rotating night shift were underweight than nurses without night shifts and had more-unhealthy dietary behaviors.
Seychell et al., 2016 [27]	cross-sectional, Malta	Effect of shift work on dietary intake among nurses working in general hospitals in Malta.	123 nurses	A questionnaire to investigate shift work, life style, anthropometric measurements and a food frequency questionnaire (FFQ) was used.	Shift working nurses had higher intakes of JF compared to day nurses. 40 % of nurses had fat intakes higher than the recommendations
Mandoura et al., 2017 [2]	cross-sectional, Saudi Arabia	To examine the prevalence of JF consumption among Saudi adults in Jeddah.	400 HCWs (College education or higher)	Structured validated close ended questionnaire was filled by all the participants. Chi-square and multivariate logistic regression analysis was done to examine the risk factors.	JF consumption was high in both genders. Increased JF consumption was independently associated with education.
Al Hazmi et al. 2018 [8]	cross-sectional, Saudi Arabia	Dietary habits among different HCWs at King Abdulaziz Medical City (KAMC) in Riyadh, KSA.	388 HCWs (Residents, nurses and physicians)	The questionnaire was distributed to participants in all targeted departments. Sampling was carried out on 3 days every week until the required sample size was covered.	57% of them were females. Half of HCWs work more than 8 hours daily. Females eat more fruits and vegetables than males. Saudis are less likely to eat fruits and vegetables than non-Saudis.
Iorga et al., 2018 [38]	cross-sectional, Romania	Relationship between dietary habits and eating disorders among medical university students in Romania	91 Medical students	Socio-demographic, anthropometric, medical, and psychological data were collected. Dietary self-	69.2% of students had normal weight, 64.84% preferred to have lunch, and 23.08% eat during nights. Pharmacy students had higher emotional problems

				declared habits were registered.	tend to sleep less and skip breakfast.
Mirza et al., 2018 [13]	cross-sectional, Pakistan	Consumption of JF among students of medical university Karachi, Pakistan	370 Medical students	Self-administered questionnaire consisting of 26 questions were used to collect data to assess the knowledge and health consequences regarding JF consumption.	92% were consuming JF. 34.9% reported hygiene problems, 95% gastrointestinal issues and 20% dental problems. JF intake linked with feeling drowsiness/lethargic
Monaghan et al., 2018 [10]	cross-sectional, USA	Factors that affect the eating practices of hospital nurses during their shifts.	20 nurses	Semi-structured interviews grounded in the Social Ecological Model focused on individual, interpersonal, organizational, and public policy factors affecting intake.	Nurses' perceived inability to take breaks. Presence of unhealthy food options, regulations restricting nurses' ability to eat in the workplace, affects their practice.
Shree et al., 2018 [36]	cross-sectional, India	JF pattern among medical students and factors contributing to its consumption by the students.	120 medical students	Data collection was done using pre-tested structured questionnaire and was analyzed using SPSS latest version.	Most of the students taking JF as an alternative to dinner. Most preferred beverage was carbonated drinks while preferred FF was pizza.
Veena et al., 2018 [31]	cross-sectional, India	Extent of obesity among study subjects, to assess JF eating habits and factor affecting obesity.	237 medical students	Pretested semi-structured questionnaire by interview technique. Obesity among study subjects was assessed using BMI	Ice creams & chocolates were (47%) and KFC was (52%). Factor increasing JF was taste preferences (80.5%). Obesity was linked with family history of obesity and JF eating
AlJaber et al. 2019 [42]	cross-sectional, Saudi Arabia	Pattern of eating habits and to define its association with stress among medical students.	105 medical students	The Academic Stress Scale (ASS) and compulsive eating scale (CES) were used to assess eating habits and some factors related to it	Freshman have higher stress levels than sophomores and junior, spread of FF increases the chance for students to eat unhealthy foods, and students with high stress levels eat more JF.

Pérez-Fuentes et al., 2019 [33]	cross-sectional, Spain	Role of eating on the relationship between sleep quality and self-esteem in nursing professionals.	1073 nurses	Rosenberg General Self-Esteem Scale, the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), and the Three-Factor Eating Questionnaire-R18 (TFEQ-18).	Poor sleep quality and type of eating affect self-esteem. Poor sleep quality lowered self-esteem through emotional and JF eating.
Schneider et al., 2019 [24]	cross-sectional, UK	Prevalence of health-related behaviours among nurses in Scotland.	17,261 HCWs (nurses, professionals, care workers).	Scottish Health Survey and Logistic regression models to estimate the prevalence and co-occurrence of health-related behaviours.	Nurses' health-related behaviours were better than the general population but non-adherence to public health guidelines was concerning.
Terada et al., 2019 [11]	cross-sectional, Canada	Compared dietary behaviour, cardiometabolic and psychological health between 73 nurses.	73 nurses	Spearman's partial correlation and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to compare dietary behaviour between shift- and non-shift-working nurses.	Shift-working nurses exhibited shorter fasting duration, larger day-to-day energy intake variability and higher total mood disturbance score compared to non-shift-working nurses.
Alzahrani et al, 2020 [25]	cross-sectional, Saudi Arabia	Patterns of eating habits among medical students and their relationship to sociodemographic , and psychological factors	378 medical students	Data were gathered with a self-administered questionnaire encompassing questions on sociodemographics , eating habits, and psychological factors	Eating habits score was lower among students who were smokers, lived in rented places, lived alone and had separated parents. Living alone and stressed associated with eating patterns
Bashatah, 2020 [19]	cross-sectional, Saudi Arabia	Nutrition habits among adolescents from King Saud University nursing school in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.	140 nursing students	Arabic Version of Moore Index for Nutrition Self Care was used. Self-care practices related to nutrition were assessed by using a self-report questionnaire.	Most students had fair nutritional habits. Results revealed no significant associations between gender or age and nutritional score.
Dias and Dawson, 2020 [9]	qualitative, descriptive, USA	Hospital shift nurses' experiences and perceptions and healthy nutritional choices at work.	21 Nurses	Nurses were interviewed individually or in focus groups about their workplace dietary behaviors and influences.	Nursing role in restrict freedom of movement and minimize individual control. Hospital food environment is unhealthy. Free food and shift work

					influences healthy eating.
Zhang et al., 2020 [5]	Observational , China	Food supply and nutrition status during the COVID-19 response period	1,048 HCWs (doctors, nurses, public HCWs and others)	The questionnaire composed of 9 questions including participants' occupation, body weight changes during the COVID-19 response, amount and diversity of foods and overall satisfaction for the meals.	30% of HCWs thought that the dishes were too greasy. Large proportion of HCWs had unbalanced diets and 13.5% of them complained of mild discomfort after consumption.
Bin Mugren et al., 2021 [39]	cross-sectional, Saudi Arabia	Perceived stress and eating behavior among residents in a tertiary teaching hospital, KSA.	305 residents in a teaching hospital	The questionnaire evaluated stress and eating behavior using the 4-item Perceived Stress Scale and Dutch Eating Behavior Questionnaire, respectively.	Link between the level of stress and both emotions and emotional eating. A significant correlation existed between stress and abnormal eating behaviors.
Mwafi et al., 2021 [16]	cross-sectional, Jordan	Prevalence and factors related to obesity and FF consumption among university students.	503 students	Data was collected using a structured, validated questionnaire. Height and weight were measured for body mass index calculation.	Significant links between JF consumption and fried potato, processed meat products, coffee and candies. The most common reason for consumption was shortage of time.
Noor et al., 2021 [32]	cross-sectional, Pakistan	Perception of JF consumption and the associated physical and mental health problems.	200 medical students	Self-designed questionnaire to collect information on JF consumption and the various health issues emerging among medical students in Lahore.	JF consumption has been significantly associated with mental health and less physical wellbeing and risk of obesity.
Shanmugapriya et al., 2021 [40]	cross-sectional India	Dietary eating and mental health among medical students in a private medical college	200 medical students	A questionnaire assess the dietary eating habits and to assess the various factors of mental health, i.e., stress, depression and anxiety, using Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale 21 (DASS-21)	36% were having a craving for JF and frequent consumption of canned foods, frozen foods and JF were risk factors of depression. Anxiety and stress were associated with JF consumption.

Strozyk et al., 2021 [15]	cross-sectional, Poland	Nutritional behaviors among nursing staff working different shift patterns	177 nurses	Questionnaire of Eating Behavior (QEB) as a basis to study eating behavior and opinions about food and nutrition.	Incorrect eating habits include a lack of variety in foods consumed and irregular mealtimes which are associated with snacking meals during the day.
Xie et al., 2021 [22]	cross-sectional, China	Depressive symptoms, poor sleep quality and poor diet in students at Kunming Medical University during COVID-19.	1026 medical students	Modified Chinese version of the Self-Rated Depression scale was used to evaluate the outcomes of depressive symptoms over the past 2 weeks.	Negative impact of COVID-19 on student education or employment, comprised those with poor sleep quality. Negative impact of COVID-19 was more likely to report poor diet.
Altwaijri et al., 2022 [34]	cross-sectional, Saudi Arabia	Prevalence of psychological distress and predisposing risk factors among HCWs in KSA during the COVID-19 pandemic.	1,985 HCWs (nurse, physician, professional, non-medical staff)	A self-administered questionnaire was developed, and the online survey link was circulated via email networks through a preliminary email followed by two reminder emails.	The prevalence of psychological distress reported by HCWs in KSA was high. Risk factors such as insomnia, loneliness and fear of transmission predicted elevated levels of distress among HCWs.
Bouillon-Minois et al., 2022 [28]	Prospective, France	Impact of sociodemographic, and occupational characteristics on the diet of emergency HCWs.	192 emergency HCWs (nurse, physician, and workers)	Each participant monitored twice over 24 consecutive hours. Participants also had to complete a questionnaire on their sociodemographic characteristics.	Compared to day shifts, night-shift had 8.7% lower carbohydrates, 17.6% proteins, and 18.7% lipids. During the night shift the proportion of emergency HCWs who did not drink for 4 h, 8 h and 12 h increased by 20.5%, 17.5%, and 9.1%, respectively.
Gu et al., 2022 [47]	cross-sectional, China	to evaluate psychological impact on HCWs in the Fangcang shelter hospitals	522 HCWs (doctor or nurse)	Analyze potential risk factors associated with these symptoms, including PTSS, symptoms of anxiety, depression, insomnia, and perceived stress.	25 to 39% of reported symptoms of posttraumatic stress, anxiety, depression, insomnia, and perceived stress. Nurses were more affected.

Huang et al., 2022 [3]	cross-sectional, Singapore	Association between self-regulatory eating behaviours and psychological stress was explored.	707 HCWs (nurse, doctor, allied health professional)	Self-Regulation of Eating Behaviour Questionnaire (SREBQ) was used for assessment of dietary practices, and DASS-21 for assessment of stress levels	Nurses, HCWs did not complete university education have reduced SREBQ. HCWs who reported no change in SREBQ have a higher proportion of non-stressed status. Differences between changes in SREBQ and stress levels among nurses and allied health professionals.
Miki et al. 2022 [4]	cross-sectional, Japan	Association between meal consumption and depressive symptoms among Japanese HCWs during the COVID-19 pandemic.	2,457 HCWs (doctors and nurses)	Depressive symptoms were assessed using the patient health questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9). The association between frequency of balanced meal consumption and depressive symptoms was assessed using logistic regression analysis.	The risk of depressive symptoms increased with decreasing frequency of balanced meal consumption. Odds ratios of depressive symptoms were 1.00, 1.09, 1.62, and 2.21 for balanced meal consumption categories of daily, 4-5 days/week, 2-3 days/week, and ≤1 day/week, respectively.
Utter et al., 2022 [30]	cross-sectional, Australia	Food-purchasing behaviours of HCWs and opportunities for improving the hospital food environment.	501 HCWs (nurse, doctor, professional and allied health staff)	Multiple regression models describe the associations between food purchases and indicators of healthy eating, while controlling for age, gender and work role.	> 60% of HCWs consumed JF at work and this inversely associated with indicators of healthy eating. Staff feedback prioritized strategies to make healthy meals more accessible and affordable.
Yan et al., 2022 [45]	cross-sectional, China	Factor affecting unhealthy food consumption among HCWs during recuperation.	418 HCWs (undergraduate master and doctor)	SPSS 25.0 was performed for hierarchical regression to analyze the effect of affective rumination on unhealthy food consumption via emotional exhaustion.	Affective rumination had a significant positive predictive effect on unhealthy food consumption. Family support amplified the effect of emotional exhaustion on

					unhealthy food consumption.
Chen et al., 2023 [1]	cross-sectional, China	Association between physicians' eating habits and their health perception and diseases.	9196 Chinese physicians	The questionnaire based on age, sex and the department of physicians, eating habits, health-related information such as BMI classification, perceived SHS status, and prevalence of common diseases.	Among those with the above eating habits, the prevalence rates of suboptimal health and disease were higher than among those without the above eating habits.
Deepali et al., 2023 [35]	cross-sectional, India	Adverse effects of excess calorie consumption during stress which is associated obesity and depression.	150 Medical students	A modified questionnaire was circulated among 150 1st year MBBS students aged 19–21 years at SSMC, Tumkur through Google forms. The data collected were subjected to descriptive statistics and interpreted.	> 65% of participants consumed JF in the evening. Around 46% of participants preferred weekend to consume JF. More than 70% of the participants prefer JF consumption during screen time.
El Barazi et al., 2023 [6]	cross-sectional, Egypt	To examine the relationship between university students' consumption of JF and their levels of stress, anxiety, and depression.	509 students: 95 Psychology 294 Communication 120 Pharmacy	DASS-21 was used. An association between university students' consumption of JF and their levels of stress, anxiety, and depression was assessed.	The mean total anxiety score for the group that did not consume junk food was 3.7, while it was 12.6 for the group that consumes junk food. The mean total depression score for the group that did not consume junk food was 4.04, while it was 13.4 for the group that consumes junk food.
Muhaimin et al., 2023 [23]	cross-sectional, Indonesia	Stress levels and eating behavior in students enrolled at the Faculty of Health Sciences, University as Muhammadiyah Surakarta.	88 students of Faculty of Health Sciences	Stress levels were assessed using the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10) questionnaire while eating behavior data were gathered through the Adult Eating Behavior	54.5% of students had mild levels of stress alongside an inclination toward approaching food in their behavior. There was significant relationship between stress

				Questionnaire (AEBQ).	levels and eating behavior
Kokilaa et al. 2023 [37]	cross-sectional, India	JF consumption patterns and knowledge level and nutritional status among the students.	260 students in the medical teaching institute	A semi-structured questionnaire which was framed after reviewing similar works of literature was used to assess knowledge, attitude, and practice of JF consumption.	There was association between the student's year of study and their knowledge score, suggesting that the knowledge level was higher for interns. 48% consumed junk food when they felt stressed.
Rahman et al. 2023 [44]	cross-sectional, Bangladesh	Learning behaviours of medical students at the American University of Integrative Sciences (AUIS), Barbados, during the COVID-19 pandemic.	62 Medical Students	The data collecting instrument recorded students' demographic and learning behaviour information and eating disorders (SCOFF questionnaire)	24.2% screened positive for eating disorders. Screening with the SCOFF test demonstrated that females, older (>25 years), overweight + obese, Clinical Sciences + PreMed, and non-USA-based students were at more risk of eating disorders.
Yaman et al., 2023 [21]	cross-sectional, Turkey	Relationship between perceived stress, emotional eating, and nutritional habits in HCWs during the COVID-19 pandemic.	405 HCWs (specialist, dentist, nurse, physiotherapist and laboratory)	Emotional Eating Scale, Perceived Stress Scale, and Nutrition Change Process Scale were used. Data on weight, height, and changes in eating habits during the pandemic to analyze how the pandemic affected dietary and nutritional practices.	Economic concern and concern about finding food and water due to COVID-19 were found to affect changes in eating and dietary habits. Losing a loved one because of COVID-19 was determined as an independent risk factor for eating and dietary habits.
Alnajar, 2024 [41]	cross-sectional, Iraq	Incidence of JF consumption and its impact on the health of Iraqi medical students.	628 students Iraqi medical universities	Data on medical students' knowledge, attitudes, and habits about fast food intake was obtained using a 26-item questionnaire.	There was significant correlation between obesity and fast food. A substantial correlation was found between the eating of unhealthy food and feelings of tiredness or lethargy.

Badrasawi et al., 2024 [18]	cross-sectional, Palestine	Stress levels among dentists in Palestine, identify factors contributing to stress.	271 dentists	The Maslach burnout inventory was utilized to measure burnout across emotional exhaustion, and reduced personal accomplishment dimensions, while the 10-item perceived stress scale was employed to measure stress levels	Emotional exhaustion was a prominent aspect of burnout, with 48% had high levels with significant association between stress scores and female participants, daily sleeping hours, as well as emotional exhaustion and personal burnout sub scales.
Fatima et al., 2024 [26]	cross-sectional, Pakistan	Changes in dietary pattern of medical and dental students can impact their quality of life	190 medical and dental students	Validated online questionnaire having 30 questions divided into four sections. The responses were scaled in three tiers and the data was analyzed using statistical software	32.6% of students rated their quality of life as good with respect to dietary habits while 81.6% rated physical environment as moderately healthy with very many difficulties in concentrating and poor physical energy levels. Negative feelings were frequent and a majority noted changes in eating habits with increase BMI
Naik et al., 2024 [12]	cross-sectional, India	Patterns of consumption of JF among young adults and to explore the reasons for JF consumption among young adults	116 Medical students	Mixed method study consisting of quantitative phase using a semi-structured, validated questionnaire circulated through Google Forms followed by an depth interview of 10 participants for qualitative phase	The most common reasons for JF consumption were its good taste and convenience. The qualitative interview also supported the findings that the most common reasons for JF consumption were craving, inexpensive, taste, and poor taste of hostel food
Pinto et al., 2024 [43]	cross-sectional, Brazil	Verify the food consumption of health professionals and students in the context of the	362 HCWs (health professionals and students)	The questionnaire contained questions about personal and socioeconomic characteristics,	A higher percentage of participants, regardless of COVID-19 prevalence, reported consuming

		COVID-19 pandemic in Rio de Janeiro		COVID-19, questions about sleep, mood, supplement use and food consumption.	healthy foods the day before compared to unhealthy foods. The participants' perception of a change in mood and sleep, and that this change may have led to changes in food consumption
Shafiq et al., 2024 [17]	cross-sectional, Pakistan	The relationship between dietary choices and mental health among college students	144 Medical students	7-day Food Frequency Questionnaire (FFQ), the Generalized Anxiety Disorder 7-item scale (GAD-7), and the Patient Health Questionnaire 9-item scale (PHQ-9) were used.	70% of participants suffered from depression. Anxiety affected 38.81% of students. Unhealthy eating patterns were linked to increased anxiety and depression.
Tantimahanon et al., 2024 [46]	cross-sectional, Thailand	Dietary behaviors of dental professionals, influencing their dietary options	842 dental professionals	Online questionnaire was constructed to collect data from three groups of dental professionals: undergraduates (UG), postgraduates (PG), and practicing dentists (DT).	Most participants reported occasional consumption of all five main food groups and frequent ordering of vegetable-based dishes. Attitude emerged as the strongest association of healthy dietary behaviors across all groups.

Discussion

Regular JF consumption is linked to oxidative damage, systemic inflammation, and obesity and belly fat growth. Increased intake of JF may be the initial cause of metabolic syndrome, diabetes, and heart disease [7-11].

Prevalence of JFs consumption habits among different HCWs

According to a different study on medical undergraduates, eating JFs is common among them even if there is information regarding their negative consequences [12]. Another study on medical students found that they have a partial awareness of the dangers of long-term intake of high-sodium, trans-fatty acid-rich JFs and soft carbonated drinks with artificial phosphate added [13].

A group of medical workers, including primary care doctors and nurses, who operate under extremely

stressful situations were shown to consume more harmful goods [14]. According to a study by Strozyk et al., nurses who work two shifts and frequently go for snacks in between meals have low levels of both beneficial and harmful nutrition [15].

JFs consumption with gender differences

Male students consumed more JF than female students, and they also reported worse eating habits and increased levels of worry and sadness. Previous researches have observed such gender disparities, indicating that women are more inclined to prioritize nutrition and health, leading to healthier food choices [2, 16, 17].

Due to biological, social, and cultural factors, women may experience pressure to juggle work and home obligations. Female doctors, who often served as the major caregivers in their families, had to balance the demands of their personal life with the provision of

high-quality healthcare to their patients, which might be taxing on them without sufficient assistance [18].

In a recent Saudi study, Bashatah revealed that, most students had fair nutritional habits but with no significant associations between gender or age and nutritional score [19,51]. However, numerous studies indicate that emotional eating affects women more than males, resulting in more weight gain. It is recommended that men engage in outdoor activities in a healthy way, play sports on a regular basis, decompress, and develop healthy interests and pastimes that can help them cope with stress and manage their physical and mental well-being [20, 21].

According to Xie et al., during outbreaks such as COVID-19, males were more likely than females to have poor food control and depressive symptoms, whereas females were much more likely than males to have poor sleep quality [22].

The criteria for stress levels are the same for men and women, according to Muhaimin and colleagues; nevertheless, women are more likely to have eating disorders, sleep difficulties, mood swings, and guilt. The hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis and the sympathetic nervous system, which produce negative feedback during stressful situations, biologically affect stress levels in both men and women. Oxytocin and estrogen, which are essential for regulating stress, are generally found in larger concentrations in women than in men. As a result, women are typically more vulnerable to HPA axis activation [23].

Barriers to healthy eating habits at the workplace **Organizational barriers to healthy eating**

Maintaining a balanced diet was challenging for HCWs who worked long hours and night shifts. During extended duty hours, they favored eating in bulk when they had the chance to rest since they were unsure of when they would get another chance to eat. High-energy foods like chocolate and crisps were the meal choices of HCWs working night shifts. Due to cafeterias' limited hours, they frequently relied on high-calorie items from vending machines during peak work hours [9].

Personal barriers

Emotional JF eating, the desire to consume chocolate, sweets, and JFs that are heavy in fat and sugar, was linked to job stress. Participants also mentioned how exhausting shift work made it difficult for them to adopt healthy eating habits. Chips in their pockets were cited by nurses as a quick and easy way to eat while on the job [9].

Workplace social barriers

Unhealthy eating habits are frequently influenced by coworkers who bring unhealthy food to work and by patients' family, who frequently bring candies. According to one study, nurses often eat cakes or cookies that are supplied by patients and family

members when they are hungry and exhausted [10]. Free food is frequently provided by leaders as a reward, a present for events, or even as a bribe to attend meetings. The detrimental effects of free food on their healthy eating habits were eloquently explained by one nurse [9].

Workplace physical environment

According to nurses, bad food is easily accessible. Some nurses' decisions to eat healthily were influenced by the costs of the canteen. Alternatively, there weren't always enough alternatives for nutritious eating. Only nutritious foods should be served in the canteen, according to nurses [24].

The quality of the food provided by hospital catering is deemed poor by some HCWs. Unhealthy eating patterns have been identified as a prevalent modifiable risk factor for chronic conditions such as metabolic syndrome, diabetes, obesity, and cardiovascular illnesses [8].

Because there were disproportionately healthier food alternatives available than good ones, the hospital's food environment had a significant impact on the dietary habits of HCWs. In the hospital, there were three primary ways to get food: 1) Purchasable food, including cafeteria and vending 2) brought-in food (such as lunches), and 3) free food, which was any type of food, candy, or drink that was given away without charge. In the hospital setting, free food was commonly offered and typically located near HCWs, which affected consumption [9].

Participant's demographics, job nature and JF consumption

Despite having sufficient knowledge about good eating habits, medical students don't seem to be able to use this knowledge. Their eating habits are adversely impacted by the stress of medical school and university life [25].

Eating habit is influenced by a wide range of elements, including as personal traits, social interactions, the physical environment, macroenvironmental factors, living situations of students, social dynamics, lifestyle choices, and test pressure. It is important to note that people who are feeling good often eat more than people who are feeling bad or indifferent [23].

According to Fatima's findings, one explanation for why students frequently utilize JF is that they have busy academic schedules and use it to save up time for research and study because it is easy to make and easily available. JF is usually readily accessible and packaged in a ready-to-eat form, which makes it more easy to consume than cooking at home. Additionally, because they mostly choose JFs, students living away from home are more likely to experience dietary alterations, which have a negative influence on their health [26].

Medical students may choose JF because of the long college days and everyday exhaustion. Furthermore,

over 50% of them skip breakfast, which may be connected to their increasing intake of JF, snacks, and soft beverages [6].

Due to a rapidly increasing socioeconomic position at both the governmental and civilian levels, Saudi Arabia's eating habits have changed significantly over the past few decades. Different age groups have been impacted by these significant changes in lifestyle, particularly students, who consume more animal products and processed diets than fruits and vegetables in Saudi communities [25].

Some nurses experience additional stress due to linguistic and cultural barriers, on top of the typical pressures in nursing work. The relationship between job-related stress and food consumption is influenced by cultural variations and nurses who are recruited from other nations. This suggested that psychosocial working circumstances and eating patterns were linked to cultural variations [14].

Seychell and Reeves found that compared to day nurses, accident and emergency nurses who worked shifts had higher BMI, waist circumference, and JF intakes [27].

Doctors from the nutrition department had relatively healthy eating habits, meaning they ate more meals at home, brought their own food to work, and had regular and adequate eating times, according to Chen et al.'s analysis of the differences in eating habits and disease prevalence among doctors from various departments. Accordingly, compared to other departments, nutritionists have a very low occurrence of common and chronic disorders [1].

According to research by Bouillon-Minois et al., emergency HCWs intake of nutrients is negatively impacted by working nights [28]. According to a large cross-sectional study by Ahmad et al., junior doctors reported longer working hours, a relatively strong desire to change careers, poorer mental scores, fewer breakfasts, lower vegetable consumption, and higher fruit intake than senior doctors. Compared to doctors and nurses, dentists had the highest levels of mental wellness [29].

Overweight and obesity among HCWs

Excessive adipose tissue accumulation in the body is a hallmark of obesity, which is categorized as a risk factor for a number of illnesses, including cardiovascular conditions with a consequence of social, economic, and genetic forces. Additionally, lifestyle, sleeping patterns, daily activities, home environment, and eating habits all affect how this illness spreads [16]. Obesity and poor nutrition are prevalent among HCWs [30].

31.5% of the doctors were overweight or obese, based on the BMI categorization used from the Chen et al. dataset [1]. Age group, family history of obesity, and frequency of JF eating were shown to be significantly associated with obesity, according to Veena et al.'s

research [31]. However, characteristics such as sex, family type, religion, and socioeconomic position did not significantly correlate with obesity. According to Terada et al., hospital nurses' food habits were strongly correlated with their risks for cardiometabolic disease. Frequency of snacking was directly correlated with body fat percentage, while daily fluctuations in energy consumption were positively correlated with waist circumference and BMI [11].

According to the Noor et al. study, a sizable portion of students (70%) gained weight and were obese as a result of including JF in their diets [32]. Another research by Mwafi et al. found that JF consumers had a higher prevalence of obesity (29.9%) than non-consumers (9.1%) [16]. Because JF has a high energy content, it is strongly correlated with weight growth and obesity. Consuming JF is closely linked to becoming overweight or fat. Burgers, pizza, sandwiches, and fried chicken are among the foods found in JF that have contributed to the rise in obesity [32].

The study by El-Barazi et al. emphasizes how JF will impact a person's emotions and increase their susceptibility to stress, anxiety, and depression. Students' body mass index is negatively impacted when they consume JF. Because JF is high in calories and low in nutrients, it has been associated with a higher risk of being overweight [6].

Impact of JFs on mental health and work outcomes among HCWs

HCWs face a variety of stressors, such as financial strains, the workplace, chasing new treatment technologies, and a heavy job that includes weekends and nights. They may also feel overburdened by the volume of patients they encounter on a daily basis. They also have trouble handling the challenges of everyday life, such as interpersonal disputes and health issues [18].

According to a Saudi study by Altwaijri et al., stress is strongly linked to choosing unhealthy foods. These circumstances may cause stress in certain kids, which may impair their appetite and cause them to skip meals. They consumed JFs and displayed poor eating habits [34]. JF intake and drowsiness/ lethargy were found to be significantly correlated by Mirza et al. [35]. Emotions such as happiness, sadness, anger, worry, etc. were found to be significant factors in JF intake by Shree et al. Of the medical students in their research, 23.3% disagreed with this fact, whereas 55% concurred. All of the individuals continue to eat JFs mostly because they find it pleasant, even though the majority (88.3%) are aware that doing so causes a number of illnesses and disabilities [36].

According to Noor et al., consuming JFs deteriorates mental health. Consuming JFs has been found to be substantially linked to mental health problems. Consuming JFs was also linked to an increase in the

likelihood of obesity and a decline in physical health. Intake of JFs was shown to be significantly correlated with improvements in mental health issues. Intake of JFs also found to be associated with anger and depression [32]. However, Kokilaa and coworkers found a little impact of JF consumption on physical wellbeing, morbid disease, anxiety levels, global warming, everyday emotions, mental health, or sleep quality [37].

Additionally, Terada et al. found that poor self-esteem, personal estrangement, and interoceptive deficit—all broad psychological measures that are pertinent to eating disorders—were adversely correlated with calorie and fat consumption. They believe that nutrition restriction was caused by the psychological susceptibility of female nurses [11]. These are comparable to findings of Iorga et al., who found that psychological ratings were negatively correlated with a propensity to restrict energy intake and skip meals among pharmacy students, the majority of whom were female (>90%) [38].

According to a research by Bin Mugren et al., residents who consumed JF had a higher subjective level of stress. Additionally, because of their expertise, residents' eating habits and stress levels were significantly correlated. These findings imply that emotional elements have a greater effect on dietary choices made by residents under stress, making it more difficult to control the quantity and quality of food consumed [39].

According to Shanmugapriya et al., there is a statistically significant correlation between depression and gender, alcohol and tobacco use, and the frequency of canned and frozen food intake. It was discovered that there was a statistically significant correlation between anxiety and both tobacco and JF use [40].

El-Barazi et al. found that medical students who took JF had greater rates of depression and higher stress and anxiety ratings than those who did not [6]. In a similar vein, Shafiq et al. found a strong correlation between poor eating habits and elevated anxiety and sadness. Moderate to severe levels of anxiety and sadness were more common among medical students who consumed large amounts of refined carbohydrates and saturated fats. On the other hand, less instances of these mental health problems were linked to a larger consumption of fruits and vegetables [17].

In contrast to what was anticipated, Alnajjar showed that a considerable number of medical students eat unhealthy food despite being aware of its negative effects on their health. According to the study's findings, which are consistent with earlier studies, medical students' eating habits are similar to those of non-medical students. Indeed, it's possible that medical students are more likely to eat unhealthy foods [41].

According to AlJaber et al., first-year medical students experience more stress than sophomores and juniors. Their research indicates that 34.3% of preclinical students recognize high levels of stress when the doctor increases demands, and that the level of stress will be moderate. On the other hand, 29.5% of higher level students report lower levels of stress because they are able to control themselves during study hours, increasing their level of concentration and making it easier for them to obtain information than students in lower levels. Additionally, they report higher levels of stress during exams because they have more references, which makes it harder for them to prepare for the test than students in lower year [42].

Impact of JFs among HCWs during COVID infection

The psychological effects of COVID-19 on frontline HCWs have been covered in a number of papers. When a disease like COVID-19 breaks out, HCWs emotional reactions are complex and may have long-term effects on their mental health. Higher levels of stress, anxiety, depression, severe insomnia, obsessive-compulsive symptoms, somatization, post-traumatic stress disorder, vicarious traumatization, an increased risk of developing other mental health issues, and in the most vulnerable cases, suicide, are all signs of psychological distress among HCWs [43,52].

It has been demonstrated that psychological anxiety during the COVID-19 pandemic negatively impacts the mental and physical health of HCWs, resulting in a decline in productivity and performance. Prioritizing food quality has a significant impact on HCWs, particularly during the response phase when they are experiencing high levels of job intensity, physical and mental weariness, decreased physical activity, sleep issues, and changes in their body weight and eating habits [44].

Eating habits of HCWs are impacted by the new crown epidemic, which increases the risk of weight gain and immunological impairment, decreases physical activity and exercise, and increases carbohydrate intake. In addition to having inadequate sleep and nutrition, some first-line nurses who combat COVID-19 exhibit overtly negative emotions such worry and melancholy [1].

After spending a lot of time in a stressful workplace, front-line HCWs would have been more prone to use JF, binge eating, or other unhealthy behaviors as a way to cope with their negative feelings [45].

Miki et al. found that 364 individuals (14.8%) out of 2,457 Japanese HCWs during the COVID-19 pandemic had depressed symptoms. Compared to those who ate balanced meals every day, participants who ate balanced meals ≤ 1 day per week and 2-3 days per week experienced considerably more depressed symptoms [4].

After controlling for age, gender, nationality, marital status, having a domestic helper, and the number of days spent engaging in moderate-vigorous activity, Tantimahanon et al. found that participants who reported no change in self-regulation eating behaviors were 2.11 times more likely to be non-stressed than those whose self-regulation eating behaviors had deteriorated [46,52].

In their study of 522 individuals, Gu et al. found that mental health symptoms were highly prevalent during the COVID-19 pandemic. Overall, symptoms of anxiety, sadness, sleeplessness, perceived stress, and posttraumatic stress disorder were reported by 25.3%, 51.0%, 58.0%, 14.8%, and 39.1% of all participants, respectively [47].

Yaman et al. established a correlation between changes in emotional eating and dietary behaviors and the stress that COVID-19 induced in HCWs. The stress experienced explains the connection between the psychological impact of COVID-19 and the alteration in eating and dietary practices [21].

Conclusions

Workplace nutrition programs in healthcare settings have the potential to enhance employee health outcomes. A healthy diet is crucial for the health and happiness of HCWs. According to the present study's findings, HCWs' healthy eating habits may benefit from changes made to the retail food environment. Future studies can assess how new strategies to encourage healthier eating among HCWs affect diet quality and more general measures of health and wellbeing. Finally, researchers may look into how food service providers and merchants view potential to support better eating programs in hospitals.

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